

Paper 7

A STUDY ON SIBLING RELATIONSHIP AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Family is the key factor of every social relationship. Importance of emotional development in the family and the role of parents and children are always a matter of interest. Emotional intelligence is one of the key aspects of intelligence that touches the whole relationships in one's life. Sibling relationship is said to be the most enduring relationship in our lives. During adulthood the time spent with siblings decrease but the emotional support and closeness are significant factors. Emotional intelligence helps to interact effectively with others and it helps to relieve from stress and other negative emotions. Studies show that Emotional intelligence helps us overcome the obstacles and challenges of day today life. It enables us to work effectively. Sibling relationship can foster emotional intelligence.

Objective: The research is done to assess the role of sibling relationship on fostering emotional intelligence among college students. Design/Methodology/Approach: Quantitative analysis method with pre-established tools of Emotional Intelligence and Life span sibling relationship

Findings/Results: The results indicate that sibling relationship play a significant role in developing emotional intelligence.

Originality/Value: The study points out how sibling relationship affects emotional intelligence

Paper type: Quantitative analysis

Key words: sibling relationship, emotional intelligence, college students, adulthood

1. INTRODUCTION

Our first and greatest emotional memories are formed in our families, and they continue to appear there. This is why emotional intelligence (EI) succeeds where other family harmony efforts have failed. We respond to another one's needs by attending, accepting, and permanently attuned to one and others. Empathy and active awareness help us to be more attentive to other's needs. In the family, EI is extremely useful because it gives you control over your relationships with your parents and children, siblings, in-laws, and extended family. A person's emotional intelligence has been linked to successful management, social competence, and good leadership in several studies [1]. Effects of sibling relationship on prosocial behaviors and conduct problems are stronger for twins than singleton siblings [2]. The growth of a sibling relationship is favourable as the individual grows. A person's life experiences are shaped by his or her relationships with siblings. Emotional Intelligence (EI) is the ability to accurately recognise and assess our emotions, as well as to effectively communicate them in order to sustain healthy

interpersonal interactions. Developing Emotional intelligence in sibling relationships allows us to become more aware of our own needs as well as our roles and duties in offering a sense of security, belonging, and pride in being valued, loved, and respected to our family members. Adolescence marks the transition from carefree childhood to responsible adulthood. A teen is divided by opposing emotions. It's linked to an increase in risk-taking behaviors as well as greater emotional reactivity. An individual high in emotional intelligence pay attention to use, understand and manage emotions and these skills serve adaptive functions that potentially benefits themselves and others [3]. According to experts, parental connection [4] and family interactions [5] have a major impact on a person's emotional intelligence. Adult sibling relationships, like childhood sibling relationships, can have a significant impact on a person's life. Sibling relationships are some of the most long-lasting in people's life [6]. A series of research on emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationships were undertaken by many researchers explain that emotionally intelligent people have higher perspective taking and social skills, according to these authors [7]. They're also more cooperative and have a stronger sense of self-control. Emotion recognition, or the ability to express and understand emotions in others, is a key element of daily interactions and interpersonal relationships. Self-awareness as a psychological state in which people are aware of their own characteristics, feelings, and behaviours, Self-awareness is being developed and an important component of emotional intelligence [8]. Children try to understand emotions through bonding with their parents, teachers, peers, and others and modelling them [9]. Emotional intelligence has been connected to success and achievement [10],[11] character, neurophysiology, and cognitive enhancement [12],[13] family, school, circle of friends [14],[15] and so on are all important predictors of adolescent emotional intelligence.

1.1. Emotional intelligence has four key aspects:

(a) Perceiving Emotions: Accurately perceiving emotions is the first step toward understanding them. Understanding nonverbal signs such as body language and facial expressions may be required in many instances.

(b) Using emotions to promote thinking and cognitive activity: The next stage is to use emotions to enhance thinking and cognitive activity. Emotions aid in the prioritisation of what we pay attention to and react to; we emotionally react to things that catch our attention.

(c) Understanding Emotions: Our perceptions of emotions can have a wide range of meanings. An observer must understand the origin of someone's anger and what it can signify if they are showing furious emotions. Sibling relationships are the total of the interactions (physical, verbal and non-verbal communication) of two or more individuals who share knowledge, perceptions, attitudes, beliefs and feelings regarding each other from the time that one sibling becomes aware of the other [16]. An individual high in emotional intelligence pay attention to use, understand and manage emotions and these skills serve adaptive functions that potentially benefits themselves and others [17]. Sibling interaction and support is enhanced in the case of various crises. Siblings are typically viewed as potential source of support, a type of “insurance policy” in later life [18]. Early and middle adulthood is the age during which sibling-ship “tasks of nurturance, caretaking and teaching must be transformed into tasks addressing adult needs as the person becomes spouses, parents, and children of ageing parents” [19]. Nurturing emotional intelligence, warmth relationship, and playing are being the crucial frequency codes [20]. The qualities of relationships worked dynamically in two ways simultaneously. Learning between

children and parents can be supported by parental treatment of children's reactions and disputes, parental involvement, early contact in sibling relationships, childhood habits, and emotional intelligence teaching strategy.

1.2. Need and significance

Youth is a phase of physical and psychological maturation during which a person is supposed to acquire his or her own identity as well as the abilities essential for socially responsible behaviour. It is also a period of increased emotionality, during which people experience feelings more strongly and persistently. It is critical at this stage for a child to be able to control or regulate their emotions. Emotional stability is required during adolescence. The transition from childhood to adulthood can be a seamless one if the adolescent is guided by secure, nurturing, and understanding parents in an emotionally supportive environment [21]. The present study focuses to identify the sibling relationship in connection with emotional intelligence.

1.3. Aim

To find out the relationship between sibling relationship and emotional intelligence among college students

2. OBJECTIVES

1. To find out the sibling relationship of college students.
2. To find out the emotional intelligence of college students.
3. To find out the relationship between sibling relationship and emotional intelligence college students.

3.METHOD

(a) Design: the current study is a descriptive correlation study to identify the emotional intelligence and sibling relationship of college students.

(b) Sample: 80 Undergraduate students falling in the age range of 18-21 from various colleges of Malappuram district were participated in the study.

Measurement tools

3.1 Sibling Relationship Scale [22]: The questionnaire is comprised of 48 items and is rated on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The LSRS includes six different subscales (sample questions in parentheses): adult affect (AA, "My sibling makes me happy"), adult behavior (AB; "My sibling and I share secrets"), adult cognition (AC; "My sibling is proud of me"), child affect (CA; "I remember loving my sibling very much when I was a child"), child behavior (CB; "My sibling and I often helped each other as children"), and child cognition (CC; "My sibling and I had a lot in common as children"). A higher total score on the LSRS reflects more positive attitudes toward the sibling. The internal consistency of the LSRS subscales is high (Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranged from .84 to .91).

3.2. Emotional Intelligence Scale [23]: BEIS-10 is offered as a valid and reliable measurement tool that has particular utility in situations where brevity is important. Scoring : This tool were easily scored as all questions are positive direction 5 point Likert scale "5=Strongly Agree",4="Agree",3="Neutral" 2="Disagree" ,1="Strongly disagree" total score ranges from 10-50

3.3. Data analysis

The data were collected using Google form and entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The quantitative study data is analyzed using SPSS.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Correlation between the relationship between subscales of sibling relationship and emotional intelligence. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Sibling relationship. The subscales of sibling relationship that is adult affect and adult behaviour are significantly related to Emotional intelligence. The subscale of adult behaviour is correlated with emotional intelligence (0.551**). Adult behaviour subscale is correlated with (.530**). Other subscales of sibling relationship are not significantly correlated with emotional intelligence. Adolescent's family climate has significant relationship with the different dimensions of emotional intelligence, except interpersonal efficacy [24]. Emotional intelligence and sibling relationship are significantly correlated (.552**). There is significant association between emotional intelligence and overall sibling relationship of respondents. Emotional intelligence is predictor of sibling relationships and vice-a-versa, so, it can be said that sibling relationships and emotional intelligence are bi-directional in nature, one influencing the other [25]. Thus, there is a role of sibling relationship in developing emotional intelligence.

5. CONCLUSION

Emotional intelligence and sibling relationship are interconnected. Family ecosystem is a massive element that mother and father can impact the nice of sibling relationships. The relationship among siblings assists to enhance, rebuild, and consolidate supportive relationships with every other.

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